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The Mediating Effect of Cultural Benefit in Supporting Participation to Gastronomy Cities Network: The Case of Denizli Province

Abstract

This study analyzes the mediating effect of cultural benefit in supporting participation to gastronomy cities network for sustainable development. This study was conducted with the purpose of contributing in the participation of Denizli province to gastronomy cities network by ensuring sustainability of local food. The questionnaire was implemented on the managers and/or owners of volunteering food and beverage businesses in Denizli province. Demographic questions used nominal scale while other questions used 5-point likert scale. Questionnaires were distributed among food and beverage businesses in Denizli province and 146 of these were answered. Variance-based partial least squares structural equation modeling method was used to analyze the research model. Analysis of the data showed that cultural benefit has a mediating effect between gastronomy factors and support. The contribution of the study is that cultural benefit has an important effect in supporting the participation to gastronomy cities network.

Keywords: *Gastronomy, Gastronomy cities, Cultural, Gastronomy cities network.*

Jel Codes: **L80, L83, Z32**

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1. Introduction

Destinations need to create different experiences in competing conditions in order to attract more visitors (Can, 2015). The list of intangible cultural heritage assets, geographical indications and creative cities network are quite important in terms of destination awareness. The Intangible Cultural Heritage list, which was adopted by UNESCO's Convention for the Safeguarding of Intangible Cultural Heritage in 2003 and which was adopted by Türkiye in 2006, includes; traditional craftsmanship such as copperworking, weaving, filigree, folkloric

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architecture; social practices, tradition and festive events such as engagement, wedding, and birth; oral traditions and narratives such as myths, legends, tales; performance arts such as dance, theatre; knowledge and practices regarding nature and universe such as traditional food etc. (Gürçayir, 2011; Oğuz, 2009; Oğuz, 2013). In scope of traditional food which considered in the category of knowledge and practices regarding nature and universe, Türkiye has the following assets registered in the Intangible Cultural Heritage List: Turkish Coffee Culture and Tradation, Flatthread Making and Sharing Culture, Mesir Macunu Festival and Ceremonial Keşkek Tadation (Unesco, 2021a). Other than these, Türkiye has other assets that are considered as geographic indications.

There are 941 products in our country with geographical indications (Türk Patent ve Marka Kurumu, 2021). In terms of local foods, Denizli province has many assets that may become traditional speciality quaranteed and geographical indications. Since the production, quality and processing of Babadağ thyme honey, Buldan chestnut, Denizli thyme, Denizli çalkarası grape, Kale pepper, Honaz cherry, Çameli beans and İsabey seedless grape are made within the borders of Denizli province, these were protected designation of origin, and since at least one of the production and processing phases of Babadağ keşkek, Denizli roasted chickpea, Tavas baklava, Çal pekmez and Çal wine is made in Denizli province, these were protected geographical indications with Denizli (Türk Patent ve Marka Kurumu, 2021).

In terms of local foods as cultural heritage which is important in increasing attractiveness and creating brand identity (Suna and Alvarez, 2019) are very rich Denizli province. It is very important for Denizli province to be included in the creative cities network that contributes in the destinations' recognition, visibility and developing cooperation in the area of gastronomy. Creative Cities Network has been shaped around the following seven themes: gastronomy, design, music, crafts and folk arts, film, literature, and media arts (Alyakut and Küçükkömürler, 2018; Bütün and Öncel, 2019; Guimaraes et. al., 2020; Gülduran and Saltık, 2020; Nizic et. al., 2019; Popesco and Corbaş, 2012; Rosi, 2014; Sandıkcı et. al., 2020; Özdemir and Özdemir, 2020; Yalçın, 2016; Yu and Sun, 2019; Yılmaz et. al., 2020). Being recognized as a gastronomy city by UNESCO Creative Cities Network enables protection of local food and cuisine and handing over these to future generations. Thus, the purpose of this study is to analyze the mediating effect of cultural benefit in the consideration in scope of the category of gastronomy cities.

2. Literature Review

Denizli culinary culture and cuisine is rich in terms of vegetable and herb dishes, especially in terms of eggplant dishes (Çerikan, 2019). Denizli province's local foods include; acılı kavurma, araka, arap aş, aşure, amedi böreği, ala çorba, akaşı tatlısı, alaçora, biber-taze fasulye tatarı, yağda kızartılmış çitir biber, kuru biber turşusu, bakla kaynatması, baklava, balcan soğan, buğday göllesi, bedren balkabağı böreği, biberli katık dolma, bahar gevreği, bükme, biber tatarı, biber dolması, bulamaç tatlısı, biberli tavuk incik, taratorlu börülce salatası, etli bamyas, bakla tarator, börülceli kabak, kabak dolması, bakla haşlama, bakraç yoğurt, börülce gevreklemesi, börülce salatası, börülceli tarhana çorbası, börülce böreği, kedi börülce çorbası, kuru börülce çorbası, cızlama, çakır turşusu, çırpı kızartması, çağla dövmesi, cerpleme, çırpıcı göveci, çaput aş, çitlembik dolması, çığırdek tatlısı, çörekli taş ekmeği, çoban helvası, çiğ sarma, cevrit, çiğ dolma, Denizli kebabı, domates çorbası, zeytinyağlı dolma, depit aş, dolama, dıgan katmeri, dişli balık dolması, damat surası, doğrameç, düğün kolacı, erişte çorbası, erikli et kavurma, et kapama, erik çöreği, etli yaprak sarması, ev makarnası, erik pestili, erik ezmesi/ekşisi, ebe gümecisi salatası, filiz salatası, fasulye, fasulye çorbası, cizme kuru fasulye, erikli kuru fasulye, ekşili taze fasulye, kuru fasulye, taze fasulye tatarı, etli bakla fasulyesi, kara fasulye aş, etli gevrek, göce aş, göceli yaprak sarması, gölle, gazoz, günbalı, gındıra çorbası, garma gatma, gelin turşusu, gavurma aş, gaygımaş, haşhaş

sürtmesi, haşhaşlı katmer, haşhaş ezmesi, hamur dolması, irmik tatlısı, ısıra, saçta işkembe, irmik, un helvası, içli dışlı pide, incir dolması, kabuk dolması, kuru patlıcan dolması, patlıcanlı gömme, kuru biber dolması, kuru patlıcan yemeği, keşkek, keşkek üstü kavurma, kuyu tandır, kıkırdak beyzimbese, köğtü, kabak aşısı, katmer, kiide, köytü, kölle, kazan kapatma, kol dolması, kaymak baklavası, kiremitte balık, köz turşu, karışık etli dolma, kömbe, kendir ezmesi, kaşık helvası, kuyruk helvası, kaçamak, kara halva, kuzu kebabı, kavurmalı tarhana çorbası, kabak tatlısı, kumbar dolması, leyen böreği, lahana yemeği, leblebi, mısır gömbesi, meneviş yoğurtlama, mumbar dolması, mercimek gevreği, nohutlu et, nohut aşısı, nohut kavurması, sulu kavurma, ovmaç çorbası, otlu pide, oğmaç, ovalamaç, pekmez, pestil, peksimet, etli kuru dolma, etli kuru patlıcan dolması, patlıcan közlemesi, patatesli bakla, patlıcan yoğurtlaması, patlıcan ekşilemesi, pekmezli top helva, pekmez bulumbacı, pekmez bulumacı, yoğurtlu patlıcan közlemesi, yoğurtlu patlıcan gömmesi, pancar kavurması, pelte, patatesli bakla, pişi, pırasa çorbası, patlıcan kebab, patlıcan kapama, patlıcan gömme, pekmezli tatlı, pekmezli baklava, peleze, sıyırma, saraylı tatlısı, sütlü ot yemeği, sütlü simit, soğanlı gevrek, muhacir somunu, muhacir böreği, Süller pidesi, soğan böreği, sütlü corba, sütlü incirli tatlı, buldan simidi, soğan yahnisi, soğan aşısı, siron, sura, sirkeli et, şipit, şakşuk yemeği, etli top tarhana, tarhana çorbası, tirit, tandır, tutmaç çorbası, tesbi aşısı, top tarhana aşısı, telem helva, tavuk ekşilemesi, topalak aşısı, tana aşısı, Tavas baklavası, armut turşusu, etli topca, Kale baklavası, tavuklu-nohutlu taze tarhana çorbası, toga aşısı, tenem helva, ballı tahanlı pide, topalak, şepit, bezdirme, Tavas göveci, tas kapama, un çorbası, kabak çiçeği dolması, topça, mürdümeç aşısı, lahana sarma, irmik helvası, limon çorbası, üç kulak tatlısı, tez turşu, doğrameç, haranı turşusu, gömbe, boranı, bakla sıyırtması, yoğurtlama, yanık kokulu yoğurt, koyun yoğurdu, yalancı köfte, yaprak sarma, yavan tarhana aşısı, yuvalama and yufka (Başkan, 2014; Çerikan, 2019; Denizli İl Kültür ve Turizm Müdürlüğü, 2021; Erdoğan and Akay, 2018; Türkiye Kültür Portalı, 2021; lezzetler.com; Denizli Büyükşehir Belediyesi Kültür Yayınları, 2016; yemek.com; Denizli İl Kültür ve Turizm Müdürlüğü, 2020).

As a powerful, successful destination marketing tool (Ajanovic and Çizel, 2015; Akkuş and Yordam, 2020) UNESCO Creative Cities Network is an initiative that brings together 116 different cities in terms of population, capacity and incomes (Unesco, 2021b). Started in 2004 with the purpose of increasing cultural diversity and supporting development, creative cities network aims to include cultural and creative industries in sustainable development plans, to enable investments in creativity for cultural interaction, to ensure access and participation to cultural life, and to consolidate international cooperation (Alyakut and Küçükkömürler, 2018; Bütün and Öncel, 2019; Gülduran and Saltık, 2020; Namyslak, 2014; Popescu and Corbo, 2012; Rosi, 2014; Yalçın, 2016).

Gastronomy theme is included in UNESCO Cities Network which is shaped according to the cities' geographical location, history, climate and nature (Erdoğan and Özdemir, 2018; Üzümcü et. al., 2017). The scope of gastronomy theme includes the following gastronomy cities: Burgos (Spain), Gaziantep (Türkiye), Tucson (United States of America), Belém (Brazil), Bergen (Norway), Dénia (Spain), Ensenada (Mexico), Parma (Italy), Phuket (Thailand), Rasht (Iran [Islamic Republic]), Hatay (Türkiye), Afyonkarahisar (Türkiye) (Unesco, 2021a). When a city joins the network as a gastronomy city, contributions are made in the cities' national and international recognition, their development, visibility, awareness level, sustainable development, creation of brand image, international branding, crating experiences that include history and cultural values, protection of local products, ecologic production techniques and producers, revealing local values, promotion, protection of the culture and handing over this to the next generations, increase in production of local food preparation equipment, protection, diversity, sustainability, access and national and international promotion of local foods, mobilizing potential tourist groups, increase in tourist numbers, increase in hotel occupancy rates, increase in the length of stay, development in

economic and social terms, development of cooperation initiatives, increasing employment with new investments, gaining competitive power and development of the region (Akkuş and Yordam, 2020; Ajanovic and Çizel, 2015; Güler et. al., 2017; Giritioğlu et. al., 2016; Gülduran and Saltık, 2020; Gürbüz et. al 2017; Özdemir and Aydoğdu, 2021; Pearson and Pearson, 2017; Taştan and İflazoğlu, 2018; Yıldız and Olcay, 2020).

The studies conducted with regard to UNESCO Creative Cities Network include studies analyzing; the relation between traditional culture and creative city approach, definition of gastronomy city criteria, the role of creative cities in regional development, advantages provided by creative city network, experiences of creative cities, creativity process in tourism, the case of Antalya province as a creative city, the role of Instagram in Macau's becoming a gastronomy city, the case of Kilis province in the category of gastronomy, crafts and handicrafts in the creative city network, analyzing Kastamonu cuisine according to creative city network's gastronomy criteria, the impacts of application processes of Barcelona and Glasgow, the case of George Town as a gastronomy city, stakeholders' awareness in the application of Kastamonu to be registered as a gastronomy city in the creative cities network, evaluation of Kocaeli province in terms of gastronomy theme of creative cities network, comments on whether Mardin province may become a gastronomy city registered in the creative cities network, gastronomic heritage process of Florianopolis as a gastronomy city, Bitlis province's participation in creative cities network in the theme of gastronomy, cuisine of Afyonkarahisar as a gastronomy city in the creative cities network, change in Gaziantep province after it had become a gastronomy city, whether cities which earned the title of gastronomy city use this title in their websites as a promotion and marketing tool, policy suggestions for the membership monitoring report of gastronomy city Gaziantep province, definition of destination food image for gastronomy city of Gaziantep, awareness of restaurants business owners with regard to Hatay's title as a gastronomy city, the perspectives of local people in gastronomy cities of Gaziantep and Hatay provinces after these cities had been registered in the creative cities network, advantages of being included in UNESCO creative cities in gastronomy for Gaziantep province, process of creating a brand together with the cities which became successful as gastronomy cities and United Nations, websites of the cities that were registered in the creative city network in the theme of gastronomy (Ajanovic and Çizel, 2015; Akdu and Akdu, 2018; Akkuş and Yordam, 2020; Akın and Bostancı, 2017; Alyakunt and Küçükömürler, 2018; Bütün and Öncel, 2019; Demirtaş and Pektaş, 2020; Emmendoerfer et. al., 2016; Guimaraes et. al., 2021; Güler et. al., 2017; Gürbüz et. al., 2017; Giritlioğlu et. al., 2016; Khoo and Badarulzaman, 2014; Nizic et. al., 2019; Özdemir and Aydoğdu, 2021; Özdemir and Özdemir, 2020; Pearson and Pearson, 2017; Popescu and Corbo, 2012; Sandıkçı et. al., 2020; Taştan and İflazoğlu, 2018; Tuna et. al., 2017; Xiaomin, 2017; Yıldız and Olcay, 2020; Yılmaz et. al., 2020; Yu and Sun, 2019). Following hypotheses were constructed according to this information.

Hypothesis 1: There is a significant relation between gastronomy factors and supporting the participation of the city in the gastronomy cities network.

Hypotheses 2: There is a significant relation between gastronomy factors and cultural benefit.

Hypothesis 3: There is a significant relation between cultural benefit and supporting the participation of the city in the gastronomy cities network.

Hypothesis 4: Cultural benefit has a mediating effect in the relation between gastronomy factors and supporting the participation of the city in the gastronomy cities network.

3. Methodology

The questionnaire was implemented on the managers and/or owners of volunteering food and beverage businesses in Denizli province. Demographic questions used nominal scale while other questions used 5-point likert scale. Initially, a pilot test was conducted on 24 business managers in order to see whether the questions are understandable. Questionnaires were distributed among food and beverage businesses in Denizli province and 146 of these were answered.

Before the data were analyzed, missing value, box plot and Z values were analyzed along with extreme values and analysis was conducted to see whether the data distribution was normal. Variance-based partial least squares structural equation modeling method was utilized for testing the study hypotheses and multiple group analyses. Increasingly used and preferred in many areas of social sciences, variance-based partial least squares structural equation modeling does not require normal distribution, it is able to analyze reflective-formative variables, to reveal relations in complex models, to work with smaller sample groups without requiring big samples, and to conduct multiple group analyses (Ali et. al., 2018; do Valle and Assaker, 2015; Hair et. al., 2017; Hair et. al., 2019; Olya, 2017; Ringle et. al., 2020; Ryan, 2020; Sharma et. al., 2019).

Figure 2: Research Model.

Cronbach Alpha, rho A, Composite Reliability (CR) and Average Variance Extracted (AVE) figures were analyzed for internal consistency reliability; Moreover, factor load and average variance extracted (AVE) figures were analyzed for convergent validity; and Fornell-Larcker criteria (FLC), Cross Loading and Heterotrait-Monotrait Ratio (HTMT) figures were analyzed for discriminant validity (Hair et al., 2017; Hair et al., 2019). VAF figures were calculated for the mediating effect dimension. Confidence Interval (CI) calculation was also done since more valid information may be obtained through the distribution factor of the mediating effect (Mackinnon et al., 2007; Nitzl et al., 2016).

4. Findings

The majority of the participants were observed to be men, with 74%. 32% of the people who filled out the questionnaire consisted of people aged 36-45. The majority of the participants were married, with 82%. The table 1 depicts the factor loadings, Cronbach alpha, Composite Reliability (CR) and Average Variance Extracted (AVE) values.

Table 1. Indicator, Lodging, and Validity Indexes.

Items	Indicator Loads	Cronbach Alfa	Composite Reliability (CR)	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
Gastronomy		.929	.927	.637

G1	.800			
G2	.761			
G3	.798			
G4	.929			
G5	.748			
G6	.694			
G7	.751			
G8	.797			
G9	.652			
G10	.592			
G11	.925			
G12	.885			
G13	.840			
G14	.774			
G15	.762			
G16	.754			
G17	.861			
G18	.720			
G19	.784			
G20	.845			
G21	.936			
G22	.618			
G23	.820			
G24	.801			
G25	.828			
G26	.939			
G27	.965			
G28	.633			
G29	.642			
G30	.866			
G31	.947			
G32	.897			
G33	.814			
G34	.774			
G35	.794			
G36	.775			
G37	.796			
G38	.944			
G39	.564			
Benefit		.964	.968	.791
B1	.754			
B2	.922			
B3	.960			
B4	.900			
B5	.884			
B6	.918			
Support		.896	.896	.742
S1	.852			
S2	.850			
S3	.879			
S4	.874			
S5	.865			

The table 1 shows that the results in the range of 0.896 and 0.968 were found for composite reliability figures for internal consistency reliability with gastronomy (CR: 0.927), benefit (CR: 0.968), support (CR: 0.896); the highest Cronbach alpha figure belonged to benefit (α : 0.964), followed by gastronomy (α : 0.929) and finally support (α : 0.896).

The analysis of Cronbach alpha, Rho_A and composite reliability (CR) figures showed that these were above 0.70 (Hair et. al., 2017), so it was concluded that they have adequate internal consistency reliability figures. Factor loads were above 0.564. The analysis of indicators' factor loads showed that these ranged between 0.564 and 0.960.

For linearity which consists of very high levels of correlation in order to understand whether there is a common method variance problem between the variables, variation inflation factor (VIF) figures were analyzed and found below 3 (Hair et. al., 2019), so it was concluded that there was no linearity problem or multiple linear relation problem between variables and that the model was statistically significant.

For evaluating convergent validity, assessment of average variance extracted (AVE) figures values which consist of the total of factor loads' squares of latent variables divided by the number of indicators (Ali et. al., 2018; Hair et. al., 2017; Hair et. al., 2019) showed a range between 0.637 and 0.742. Moreover all composite reliability figures were bigger than average variance extracted values. Average variance extracted values explained more than half of the variance of the indicators on average, above 0.50 (Chin, 1998; Hair et. al., 2019) therefore convergent validity was ensured.

For discriminant validity which shows that one variable is different from other variables, Fornell-Larcker criteria (FLC), cross loading and heterotrait-monotrait ratio (HTMT) values were analyzed (Hair et. al., 2017).

Table 2. Fornell-Larcker Values.

	Support	Gastronomy	Benefit
Support	0.861	-	-
Gastronomy	0.518	0.816	-
Benefit	0.687	0.296	0.889

Cross loading figures showed that each of the indicators had the highest factor load in the variables they belong to and factor loads had 0.1 of difference between them. Fornell-Larcker Criteria (FLC) ranged between 0.816 and 0.889; heterotrait-monotrait ratio (HTMT) figures ranged between 0.301 and 0.697. Discriminant Validity was provided since the figure which is the square root of Average Variance Extracted value in each variable was bigger than the correlation coefficients between the related structures in the other structural correlation matrix and HTMT figures were below 0.90 value (Fornell and Larcker, 1981; Hair et. al., 2019; Henseler et. al., 2015).

Table 3. Heterotrait-Monotrait Ratio (HTMT) Values.

	Support	Gastronomy	Benefit
Support	-	-	-
Gastronomy	0.608	-	-
Benefit	0.697	0.301	-

Analysis was conducted in order to test the structural model as well as the degree of the effect of the latent variable on the other variable.

Table 4. Mediating Analysis.

	Criterion Values			
	Direct Effects		Indirect Effects	
	Support	Benefit	Support	Gastronomy-Benefit-Support
Predictors	β (t)	β (t)	β (t)	β (t)
Gastronomy	.514 (6.124)	.458 (4.854)	-----	.626(7.125)
Benefit	-----	-----	.485 (4.947)	

Gastronomy factors were found to have a significant ($p < 0.05$) effect on supporting participation to gastronomy cities network ($\beta = 0.514$), on cultural benefit ($\beta = 0.458$), and cultural benefit was found to have a significant effect on supporting participation to gastronomy cities network ($\beta = 0.485$).

Explained variance figures were analyzed in order to determine the explanation levels of endogenous variable in relation to the change in the exogenous variable. Path coefficients were analyzed and the correlation coefficient found as 0.514 between gastronomy and support variable was understood to be statistically significant ($p < 0.05$).

Cultural benefit is the mediating variable in the relation between two variables. Methods suggested by Baron and Kenny (1986); Nitzl and Hirsch (2016) were utilized to analyze whether cultural benefit had a mediating effect between gastronomy factors and support.

Confidence Interval (CI) calculation was also done since more valid information may be obtained through the distribution factor of the mediating effect as well as VAF values for mediator effect dimension (MacKinnon et. al., 2007; Nitzl et. al., 2016). Gastronomy factors have a significant effect on benefit ($\beta = 0.458$; $p < 0.05$), and benefit has a significant effect on supporting the participation to gastronomy cities network ($\beta = 0.485$; $p < 0.05$). VAF figures were calculated for the mediating effect dimension. If VAF figures are below 20%, no mediating effect could be said to exist (zero mediating effect); if these figures are in the range of 20%-80% ($0.20 \leq \text{VAF} \leq 80$), partial mediating effect could be said to exist; and figures above 80% ($\text{VAF} > 80$) correspond to full mediating effect (Hair et. al., 2017). Gastronomy factors were determined to effect support through cultural benefit ($p < 0.05$), since the statistically significant VAF coefficient is 0.75, partial mediating effect may be said to exist since both direct and indirect effects are significant. R^2 value also increased since this is a mediating effect. In the model without cultural benefit, R^2 value was 51.4% while the model with cultural benefit showed that this figure was explained at the rate of 62.6%. 11.2% increase in R^2 value is due to cultural benefit. Gastronomy factors effect cultural benefit, and cultural benefit supports participation. The conclusion was that cultural benefit had a partial mediating role between gastronomy and support. The model shows that cultural benefit has a significant effect on the relation between gastronomy and support, there is a cause-effect relation. Gastronomy factors have partial mediating effect since both direct and indirect effects of cultural benefit are important.

5. Conclusion, Implications and Limitations

Aiming to provide ground for Denizli province to become a gastronomy city and for sustainable development, this study assessed the potential of Denizli province to participate in the gastronomy cities network and analyzed the mediating effect of cultural benefit in the evaluation of Denizli province’s participation in the gastronomy cities network. There are many local foods in Denizli province which is quite rich in terms of cuisine. It is very important for Denizli province to be included in the creative cities network that contributes in the destinations’ recognition, visibility and developing cooperation in the area of gastronomy.

Gastronomy factors have a positive effect on cultural benefit, and cultural benefit has a significant effect on supporting participation to gastronomy cities network. When VAF value is taken into account for the mediator effect dimension, a partial mediating effect is found to exist. The correlation coefficient increases when cultural benefit is added to the equation as the mediating effect. Cultural benefit effects the relation and there is a cause-effect relation. Cultural benefit's partial mediating effect has been determined. When analysis was conducted to see whether these relations are statistically significant, the correlation coefficient between gastronomy factors and cultural benefit are observed to be significant relation is seen between cultural benefit and supporting participation to gastronomy cities network as a gastronomy city.

To support Denizli province's participation to gastronomy cities network, all kind of cultural elements that include local food should be determined, revealed, protected, and a inventory should be conducted in order to hand these over to the next generations. Materials should be developed to promote the foods in this inventory, a webpage should be designed and awareness should be raised with the aid of visual materials on social media platforms. Gastronomy routes should be created in line with the information in the inventory.

Public institutions, sector representatives, non-governmental organizations, local governments and local people should cooperate to organize food festivals and contests to promote foods in a way that promotes participation and support.

A gastronomy museum should be founded including information regarding local products with geographical indications that reflect local dishes and cuisine of Denizli province, traditional cooking methods and local materials. Moreover, documentaries should feature in the gastronomy museum with regard to local dishes.

Gastronomy areas should be created at the points which reflect the cultural identity of the city to offer local flavour. These areas should increasingly include gastronomy facilities that offer local dishes. Gastronomy facilities should establish contact with the tourism businesses in the province and forward their guests to these places for traditional flavour. In these facilities, all foods and beverages should consist of local products, traditional cuisine practices and cooking methods should be used, traditional cooking skills should be protected and the presentations should be made in the local manner. Recipes of local dishes should be recorded in these facilities, trainings should be given about cooking methods, and local food courses and culinary workshops should be organized.

A department should be established by public institutions, sector representatives, non-governmental organizations and local governments. This department should organize a Denizli gastronomy workshop in order to contribute to the participation of Denizli province in the gastronomy cities network. Future studies may analyze before and after periods of participation to gastronomy cities network and research opinions of the local people. This study was carried out only in restaurant businesses operating in the province of Denizli. In future studies, opinions of other businesses should be sought.

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